

of one maxima at 480 nm. pH was varied with the buffer. The most suitable pH lies in the range 2.4–3.0. The maximum absorbance was observed in presence of three-fold excess of the reagent. The complex obeyed Beer's law upto 40 ppm Fe^{III}. The optimum concentration range for 1-cm cell was evaluated by Ringbom⁴ plot which was found to be 16–30 ppm Fe^{III}. Sensitivity of determination and molar absorptivity were 0.048 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and $1.06 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The combining ratio of iron(III) and the reagent was 1 : 2. The stability constant of the complex was determined by molar-ratio method and was found to be $4.80 \times 10^{12} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The interference caused by various ions, viz. Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Tl^I, Ag^I, La^{III}, Sb^{III}, As^{III}, Bi^{III}, VO^{II}, Cr^{III}, UO₂^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II}, chloride, bromide, iodide, acetate, carbonate, sulphite, sulphate, nitrite, nitrate, thiosulphate, cyanide, borate, thiocyanate, persulphate, salicylate and ascorbic acid do not interfere even when present to five-fold excess. However, the excess of fluoride and phosphate seriously interfere.

References

1. C. L. SHARMA, V. MISHRA and R. S. ARYA, *Natl. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 53 session, 1983, (A/68), W. FORTUNE, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1938, 10, 60; T. C. OVENSTON and C. A. PARKER, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 3, 277; M. S. MOSS and M. G. MELLON, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 14, 862; K. MUKHERJEE, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 273; D. L. DEUSSING and L. NEWMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 552; R. A. BRCKWITH, *Chem. Ind., (London)*, 1954, 663.
2. C. L. SHARMA and V. MISHRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1986 16, 243.
3. W. C. VOSBURGH and C. R. COOPER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.
4. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1988, 115, 332.

Selective Detection of NCS⁻ with Bismuth Nitrate by Capillary Solid-state Spot-tests

ALI MOHAMMAD* and NAIM FATIMA

Department of Applied Chemistry, Z. H. College of Engineering and Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

Manuscript received 8 October 1987, revised 6 May 1988,
accepted 17 August 1988

SEVERAL methods¹ have been developed for detection, determination and separation of thiocyanate in solution, but no attempt has been made to detect NCS⁻ in solid-state. Capillary solid-state spot-test technique developed in our laboratory² provides three variables, such as the colour at the junction, the direction of movement of the coloured boundary and the length of the coloured boundary. These variables make a test more selective than wet

and powder trituration spot-tests in which only the colour formed is indicative.

Therefore, an attempt has been made to develop a selective solid-state spot-test for NCS⁻ using bismuth nitrate as reagent and allowing the reaction to occur through a glass-wool plug via vapour phase diffusion.

Experimental

Bismuth nitrate (BN) and ammonium thiocyanate (ATC) were of AnalaR grade. Anions such as Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻, Fe(CN)₆³⁻, Cr₂O₇²⁻, CrO₄²⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, BrO₃⁻, NO₃⁻, VO₃⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ were of AnalaR grade and taken as their sodium or potassium salts. Chlorides of copper, iron and tin, acetate of zinc and nitrate of chromium were used. Intimate mixture of variable concentrations of well-powdered reagent were prepared with strontium nitrate as diluent. The mixture was trituated in a small mortar till it became homogeneous.

Solid-state detection by powder trituration: The test material (6–10 mg) was trituated with well-powdered reagent in the depression of a white spot-plate, and the colour developed at room temperature (30°) was recorded.

Detection by capillary solid-state tests: The well-powdered reagent was introduced from one end of a graduated capillary (10 cm × 2.5 mm dia) and the test material was similarly packed from the other end in order to bring both the reactants into close contact in the middle of the capillary. The grinding and packing of powders were done in a reproducible manner. The colour at the junction, the direction of the movement and length of the coloured boundary were recorded at desired temperature after a fixed time interval. To study the effect of concentration of reagent on the length and direction of the coloured boundary, synthetic mixtures containing 1–10% BN with strontium nitrate were filled in capillaries in place of pure BN as described above.

Glass-wool plug modification for specific detection of NCS⁻: An air gap between the reagent and the test material was created by introducing a glass-wool plug (2–6 mm) in the middle of the glass capillary before the filling of reactants into it. The test material and the reagent were then filled from either ends of the capillary. The colour and thickness of the coloured boundary formed at glass-wool test material junction were recorded.

Results and Discussion

The anions like Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻, IO₃⁻, IO₄⁻, CH₃COO⁻, HCOO⁻, CQ₃²⁻, MoO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻, S₂²⁻, SO₄²⁻, C₂O₄²⁻ and PO₄²⁻ did not give any colour with BN when trituated on a spot plate at 30°. All these anions except HCOO⁻ produced white precipitate in solution. Cations like Hg₂²⁺, Ag⁺, Cd²⁺, Ba²⁺, Ca²⁺,

Sr^{2+} and Pb^{2+} did not produce any colour with BN. No change in colour was observed in case of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . BN produced orange or yellow colour with ATC on spot plate, with the evolution of violet gas during trituration while a white precipitate with a yellow solution were produced when their aqueous solutions were mixed in a test tube. However, when the reactants were brought in close contact in a glass capillary at 30° , a pink colour immediately appeared at the BN-ATC junction. The pink colour rapidly moved towards ATC and portion of the capillary containing ATC became pink within 5 min. The pink colour started to change to orange-yellow or yellow after 20 min. A yellow product formed on trituration of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ with BN converted into red within 5 min while a dark brown precipitate was produced in solution. NO_3^- and Zn^{2+} both gave yellow products in the solid-state but in solution they gave white precipitate. In solid-state, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ gave brown product which change to red on keeping at room temperature whereas in solution only a brown precipitate was obtained.

Of all the ions which gave coloured products with BN, I^- produced the largest boundary length towards test material, leading to selective detection of I^- . I^- can be distinguished from NO_3^- , VO_3^- , Br^- , CrO_4^{2-} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ on the basis of the boundary length at 30° or 50° . The orange and yellow product boundaries formed at 50° after 30 min by $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (4 mm towards reagent) and CrO_4^{2-} (1 mm towards test material) moved in opposite directions with different rates. Thus $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and CrO_4^{2-} can be sharply distinguished. Likewise, Fe^{3+} can be distinguished from Cu^{2+} and Cr^{3+} on the basis of the length and the direction of the product boundary. $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ both producing blue product at BN-test material junction can be distinguished easily on the basis of the boundary length at 50° .

The length of the product zone increased with time, temperature and the concentration of the reagent. Thus, an enhanced selectivity can be attained by performing capillary solid-state spot-test with lower concentration of the reagent or by reducing the reaction time. As a result, I^- and NCS^- can be selectively detected in presence of the other ions by using 1% BN at 30° . Furthermore, 1% BN can be utilised for the specific detection of NCS^- which formed a product zone of 14 mm towards the test material at 30° after 30 min. None of the ions except I^- gave any colour, which produced a yellow thin ring at the interface of the reactants.

Glass-wool plug modified capillary solid-state spot-test technique offers more effective alternative for the selective or even specific detection of NCS^- . For this purpose, a glass wool plug of 4 mm was introduced between the reagent and the test material in glass capillary. None of the ions tested gave any colour either at glass wool-reagent or glass wool-test material junction at 40° upto 4 h except NCS^-

which produced yellow boundary at glass wool-test material junction after 1 h, which may thus be specifically detected. Thus the presence of 5 or 10% NCS^- was successfully detected in the mixture containing 95% Br^- , VO_3^- , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, CrO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ or 90% NO_3^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, S^{2-} , Zn^{2+} and Fe^{2+} by observing yellow colour at glass-wool-test material junction at 40° after 2 h.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly thankful to the Chairman, Department of Applied Chemistry, Z. H. College of Engineering and Technology for facilities.

References

1. A. V. HANLEY and F. W. CZECH in "Analytical Chemistry of Sulphur and its Compounds", ed. J. H. KARCHMER, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970, Part I, p. 379; F. FREIGL and V. ANGER, "Spot Tests in Inorganic Analysis", Elsevier, New York, 1972, p. 442; W. J. WILLIAMS, "Hand Book of Anions Determination", Butterworths, London, 1979, pp. 228-38; Z. N. JOSE, G. C. A. FESSEL and L. MASSAO, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1984, 9, 45 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, 104, 1412014); H. M. STEVENS, *J. Forensic Sci. Serv. Soc.*, 1986, 26, 137.
2. M. QURESHI, H. S. RATHORE and A. MOHAMMAD, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 874.

Conductometric and Enthalpimetric Determination of Saccharin in Acetone

P. N. VYAS and R. B. KHARAT*

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Nagpur-440 001

Manuscript received 6 January 1988, revised 6 July 1988, accepted 13 September 1988

SACCHARIN is a weak acid with $\text{p}K_a$ 11.6 and finds use as an artificial sweetener. Different methods are suggested for its determination¹. The official recommended methods² use titrations with alkali in hot aqueous or alcoholic solutions. No work has been reported for the determination of saccharin in nonaqueous solvents, hence, this study was undertaken. The paper describes conductometric and enthalpimetric titrations methods of estimation of saccharin in acetone medium using two different titrants. Optimum conditions for its determination are standardised.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Saccharin (B.P.) was recrystallised twice from alcohol, dried (m.p. 223°) and its purity checked by tlc. Acetone and isopropanol were purified by method reported earlier³. Potassium hydroxide in isopropanol (alc. KOH) and tetra-*n*-butylammonium hydroxide (*t*-Bu₄NOH) in toluene-methanol were prepared as described earlier⁴.